
Soil and crop management

Screening blue-green algae types tolerant of daphnids in paddy fields

S. Srinivasan, Paddy Experiment Station (PES), Aduthurai 612101 Thanjavur District, Tamil Nadu, India

Pathogens or predators, cyanophages, bacteria, fungi, daphnids, and fish are problems in establishing blue-green algae (BGA) in the fields. But the major hurdle in the rice fields of Tamil Nadu seems to be daphnids alone. As soon as the BGA start growing in the paddy fields and even before the formation of spores (akinetes), the daphnids appear in abundance and devour the whole algal mass.

Daphnids can be controlled easily by the application of carbofuran 3G or Ekalux 5G. But the saving of 25 kg inorganic nitrogen per hectare through the use of BGA is nullified by the cost of pesticides for the control of daphnids. Use of insecticides and keeping the field without water for a few days also help, but they encourage weed growth. To find a cheap and easy solution to the problem, selection of BGA types that can proliferate in the field even with a thick daphnid population was attempted during 1980 at PES, Aduthurai.

Three separate conditions suitable for the growth and development of different BGA were created each month — planted field, field with stubbles and plowed, and prepared field. As per the field-scale BGA multiplication procedure standardized by the author, water was maintained permanently and superphosphate alone was added as nutrient for algal activity. To have a dense population of daphnids, no pesticide was applied. BGA that developed from January-December were recorded and observed for their tolerance for daphnids. A total of 62 species of BGA belonging to 18 types were recorded during the year: 17 *Anabaena*, 7 *Nostoc*, 7 *Oscillatoria*, 5 *Cylindrospermum*, 3

Aulosira, 3 *Gloeotrichia*, 3 *Lyngbya*, 3 *Microcystis*, 2 *Chroococcum*, 2 *Aphanothece*, 2 *Wolleea*, 2 *Phormedium*, and one each of *Calothrix*, *Gloeocapsa*, *Microcoleus*, *Rivularia*, *Plectonema*, and *Gloeothece*.

Among them, *Wolleea bharadwajae* and *Microcystis marginata* grew without any setback even under high daphnid populations. The additional advantage of these algae is their ability to be in the field the year-round. *Aphanothece pallida* and *Gloeotrichia raciborskii* were the next best, followed by *Chroococcus minimus*, *Aphanothece prasina*, *Gloeothece rhodochlamys*, *Rivularia aquatica*, *Plectonema boryanum*, *Calothrix brevissima*, *Nostoc verrucosum*, and *Anabaena fertilissima*.

The morphological characteristics of some tolerant species are given below:

Wolleea bharadwajae was seen in cropped as well as in fallow fields. After 2-3 weeks of submergence, the thallus first appeared as a club-shaped vesicle; later it appeared as a cylindrical finger-like structure attached to the soil substrate in clusters. It was free floating because of mechanical disturbance in later stages. The initial light blue-green color changed to light yellowish-brown later. The alga was highly gelatinous and slightly sticky.

Microcystis marginata was observed only in cropped fields. The rounded, irregularly flattened colony was seen on the soil surface as a thin sheet in a water column. The greenish blue thick mass floated in the daytime.

Aphanothece pallida was seen in cropped and in fallow fields. In cropped fields it was seen floating only in the 3-4 weeks after planting. The thallus was gelatinous, soft, light. The mature thallus was granular and dull yellow.

Gloeotrichia raciborskii was seen in cropped and fallow fields. The thallus was spherical, soft, light brownish black. In the initial stage of development the small round thallus attached itself to

some of the thread-like pieces of plant parts. After full growth, it appeared as a cylindrical worm-like structure from a distance because of the dense aggregation of algae colonies.

Chroococcus minimus was seen in plowed fields after harvest and before planting. The thallus initially was slightly gelatinous, yellowish brown, and roughly oval to round. The mature colony had various shapes and was slightly leathery.

Aphanothece prasina was seen in cropped fields (second crop) during cool weather. The young thallus was slightly gelatinous and soft. After full growth, it was brownish and slightly leathery.

Gloeothece rhodochlamys was seen in the stubbles of the first crop after harvest. The thallus initially was more or less round, later forming an expanded, light blue-green gelatinous mass.

Rivularia aquatica was seen in the first season crop of kuruvai from the 6th to the 8th week after planting. The thallus was spherical, light yellowish brown, hollow, highly glazy in appearance, and slightly gelatinous. It would not stick even if crushed with the fingers.

Plectonema boryanum was seen in fields with stubbles after harvest, and in cropped and in fallow fields. In summer it spread so much that the thallus had a diameter measuring a few meters.

Calothrix brevissima was seen with *Plectonema boryanum* during the summer months (March to June) in fallow fields. No separate colony was observed.

Nostoc verrucosum floated in water with the first-season crop immediately after planting and until 3-4 weeks. The thallus was seen sticking to some dead plant parts, and was spherical or subspherical like blue-green balls and gelatinous to feel. After sufficient growth it became verrucose, hollow, soft, and olive green in color.

Anabaena fertilissima was seen in fallow as well as cropped fields during

November-January. The thallus initially was oval or spherical and slightly gelatinous. After full growth it was hollow and brownish.

To implement the BGA technology in

Influence of nitrogen topdressing on the performance of blue-green algae

S. Srinivasan, Paddy Experiment Station, Aduthurai 612101, Tamil Nadu, India

The usefulness of blue-green algae (BGA) under nitrogen levels as high as 100 kg/ha was established earlier. To assess the influence of topdressing of nitrogen fertilizer on BGA performance, a trial was conducted in kharif 1979 with the variety ADT31. Nitrogen fertilizer was tried at rates as high as 100 kg/ha in slabs of 25 kg. A composite culture of BGA was applied uniformly to treatments a week after planting. Various nitrogen levels were applied with BGA both with and without topdressing of 25 kg N/ha 35 days after transplanting. The crop was harvested early in October. Topdressing of nitrogen fertilizer at 25 to 100 kg N/ha had no inhibitory effect on BGA performance. Yield data follow:

Treatments (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)
N ₀ +BGA 10	3.8
N ₀ + BGA 10 + N 25 topdressing	4.2
N ₂₅ +BGA 10	4.2
N ₂₅ + BGA 10 + N 25 topdressing	4.6
N ₅₀ +BGA 10	4.5
N ₅₀ + BGA 10 + N 25 topdressing	5.0
N ₇₅ +BGA 10	4.9
N ₇₅ + BGA 10 + N 25 topdressing	5.3
N ₁₀₀ +BGA	5.4
N ₁₀₀ + BGA N 25 topdressing	5.8
C.D. (C : 0.05%)	0.3

Effects of drying on the germinability of newly harvested rice seeds

Salvacion M. Galon and Manuel T. Galon, Negros Oriental National Agricultural School (NONAS), College, Bayawan, Negros Oriental, Philippines

Poor seed germination is a problem because farmers do not know how to

Tamil Nadu, the 12 BGA types will be multiplied in 1981 and distributed to State seed farms for further multiplication before distribution to farmers. ■

handle newly harvested rice seeds. The problem increases with double-cropping if the first crop is a new variety. Most improved rice varieties are weakly or moderately dormant, and so farmers are often short of seedlings and must leave portions of their fields unplanted.

An experiment using seeds of the early-maturing IR50 was conducted at the NONAS Experiment Farm in October 1980 with two objectives: to determine the effect of the number of drying days on germinability of newly harvested rice, and to find the relation between "rest days" after drying and germination percentage.

The rag doll was used: 100 selected IR50 seeds/treatment were sun-dried (on *sawali* at 6 kg seeds/m²) from 0700 to 1500 hours for 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 days then soaked in water and incubated for 48, 72, and 96 hours, respectively. The seeds were sown in a seedbed, then germination percentages were recorded every 48, 72, and 96 hours, respectively.

The germinability of newly harvested rice seeds increased with the number of days of sun-drying and with the number of days the seeds were allowed to "rest"

after drying.

Germination was maximum when the seeds were dried continuously for 4 days, "rested" for 6 days, then soaked in clean water and incubated for 48 hours.

When seeds were dried from 0 to 2 days, germination was slow (beginning 24 hours to 96 hours after incubation) and nonuniform. Rice seeds dried from 3 to 5 days germinated uniformly; germination ended within 48 hours of incubation.

The farmer can expect 10% germination if immediately after harvest he cleans rice seeds and soaks them in clean water for 24 hours, then incubates them for the next 48 hours. Drying for 1 day would give a germination of 17%; drying for 4 or 5 days, 93% (see figure).

We found that 70% of the viable seeds will sprout if induced to germinate without a rest period. One day of rest results in about 75% germination of viable seeds; 2 days will give 80%; 4 days, 90%; 5 days, 95%; and 6 days, 100%.

For germinability in relation to the interval of days of drying, the study showed a 42% increase with 0-1 day drying, 71% with 1-2 days drying, 28% with 2-3 days, 10% with 3-4 days, and 0.1% with 4-5 days.

Thus, there is no need to dry newly harvested rice seeds more than 4 days if the seeds are to be used immediately for the next crop. ■

Average percentage germination of newly harvested IR50 rice seeds with respect to length of drying. Negros Oriental, Philippines.